

NEW COMPOUNDS OF GALLIUM. PART II.

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In continuation of our work (Neogi and Nandi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 18, 399) we have succeeded in preparing some of the common inorganic compounds of the rare element gallium which have hitherto been unknown. The orthophosphate of gallium has been obtained by two different methods, viz., (i) dissolution of the hydroxide in orthophosphoric acid, and (ii) precipitated by the action of sodium hydrogen phosphate on the nitrate solution. Gallium salts of hydracids of the halogens are known, but those of oxyacids of the halogens are not known. We have been able to prepare the chlorate, iodate and the bromate in solution only, which decomposes on concentration even in vacuum evolving bromine.

As regards analysis in the case of the phosphate, the salt was first dissolved in dilute nitric acid and the phosphoric acid precipitated as ammonium phosphomolybdate. In order to determine the metal, the filtrate was evaporated to a syrupy consistency with sulphuric acid, and carefully heated over a free flame until nitric acid was expelled. The residue was moistened with hydrochloric acid, taken up with water, and the molybdenum was separated as sulphide. The metal was then precipitated from the filtrate as hydroxide by means of ammonium chloride and ammonia, which was ultimately ignited and weighed as oxide.

To analyse gallium chlorate, iodate and the basic iodate, the first one was dissolved in water and the others in dilute hydrochloric acid and the gallium was precipitated as hydroxide from the solution and weighed as oxide. To estimate the chlorine in the chlorate, the filtrate from the hydroxide was first reduced to the chloride by means of ferrous sulphate and then precipitated as silver chloride. To estimate the iodine, the original iodate solution (in dilute sulphuric acid in the case of iodate and dilute hydrochloric acid in the case of basic iodate) was run into a solution of potassium iodide containing hydrochloric acid and the liberated iodine was at once titrated with thiosulphate solution in the cold.

All the analyses were performed with the weights of substances made constant at room temperature by keeping them in air for a fairly long time.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Gallium Orthophosphate, $\text{GaPO}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

This salt was obtained by just dissolving freshly precipitated gallium hydroxide in dilute solution of orthophosphoric acid. The solution was left in a

vacuum desiccator for crystallisation but the solid thus obtained was insoluble in water. It was repeatedly washed with alcohol to free it from adhering phosphoric acid and again dried. The solid is also obtained by the addition of absolute alcohol to the solution. It is a white microcrystalline substance, insoluble in water, alcohol and ether, but soluble in dilute hydrochloric acid. (Found : Ga, 31.74 ; P_2O_5 , 32.07. $GaPO_4, 3H_2O$ requires Ga, 31.96 ; P_2O_5 , 32.42 per cent).

The same compound with identical properties was obtained as a precipitate when sodium hydrogen phosphate solution was added to a solution of gallium nitrate. The precipitate was washed with water, dried in a vacuum desiccator and then on analysis gave exactly the same composition. (Found : Ga, 32.47 ; P_2O_5 , 32.86. $GaPO_4, 3H_2O$ requires Ga, 31.96 ; P_2O_5 , 32.42 per cent).

Gallium Chlorate, $Ga(ClO_3)_3, H_2O$.

It was prepared by the double decomposition of the solution of gallium sulphate and barium chlorate until all barium were precipitated as sulphate. The filtrate was kept in a desiccator when needle-shaped white crystals appeared. The substance was washed with alcohol, recrystallised and dried. The salt is a white needle-shaped crystalline substance, soluble in water and hydrochloric acid, but insoluble in ether and alcohol. The salt is converted into chloride on heating. [Found : Ga, 20.43 ; Cl, 31.0. $Ga(ClO_3)_3, H_2O$ requires Ga, 20.67 ; Cl, 31.47 per cent].

Gallium Iodate, $Ga(IO_3)_3, 2H_2O$.

Metallic gallium was dissolved in nitric acid and the theoretical amount of iodic acid added to the solution ; the nitric acid was driven off by evaporation on the water-bath, when white crystals of gallium iodate appeared, which was subsequently washed with water and carefully dried in a desiccator over calcium chloride. This substance is sparingly soluble in water, insoluble in alcohol and ether, but soluble in dilute hydrochloric, sulphuric and nitric acids. The salt was decomposed by concentrated hydrochloric acid with the evolution of chlorine and iodine vapours evolved on prolonged boiling with concentrated hydrochloric acid. [Found : Ga, 11.06 ; I, 60.84. $Ga(IO_3)_3, 2H_2O$, requires Ga, 11.09 ; I, 60.38 per cent].

Basic Gallium Iodate, Ga(IO₃)₃, Ga₂O₃, 3H₂O.

This basic compound was obtained as a white precipitate when sodium iodate solution was added to a solution of gallium nitrate. The precipitate was washed several times with water and dried. The substance is insoluble in water, alcohol and ether, but soluble in dilute hydrochloric acid. [Found: Ga, 24.83; I, 45.26. Ga(IO₃)₃, Ga₂O₃, 3 H₂O requires Ga, 25.09; I, 45.51 per cent).

Gallium Bromate.

Gallium bromate was prepared in the same way as the chlorate, barium bromate being used in place of the chlorate. The resultant solution of gallium bromate, which was a weak one owing to the limited solubility of barium bromate, on being concentrated decomposed and bromine vapour was evolved. Hence it shows that gallium bromate is an unstable compound. Attempts were made to precipitate the gallium bromate by means of absolute alcohol, acetone, as well as alcohol and ether, but no solid bromate separated. The partly dried, salt still contained small quantities of the bromate but when the solid was completely dried there was no trace of bromine in it, and the hydrate remained.

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